

Improving Peripheral Intravenous Catheter Insertion Competency of Home Health Nurses

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Background

- Home health registered nurses (RNs) frequently required to establish intravenous access
- Peripheral intravenous catheter (PIVC) insertion is a fundamental skill
- Lack of PIVC education amongst nursing students and current RNs
- Lack of education may lead to lower levels of PIVC competence

Purpose

To develop, implement, and evaluate a PIVC insertion training program for home health infusion RNs

Objectives

- Develop and pilot a PIVC placement policy and training program
- Pilot the PIVC skills program over a 2-month period
- Evaluate and modify the PIVC program based on project results

Methods

Design: Evidence-Based Practice (EBP) Project

Setting: Small, home health organization in Orange County, CA

Sample: RNs employed between February 2021 – March 2021

Measures: Demographics, PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment, PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist

Results

PIVC Insertion Knowledge Assessment Scores

Nurse	Pre-PIVC Knowledge Score	Post-PIVC Knowledge Score	Count Change
1	11	10.5	-0.5
2	12	14.5	2.5
3	19	18	-1
TOTAL COUNT CHANGE SCORE: 1			
AVERAGE COUNT CHANGE SCORE: 0.33			

Percentage Completed of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist

Nurse	Attempt 1 – % Completed	Attempt 2 – % Completed	% Change
1	61%	83%	22%
2	86%	100%	14%
3	100%	96%	-4%
TOTAL % CHANGE SCORE: 32%			
AVERAGE % CHANGE SCORE: +10.67			

RN Demographics

Years of Nursing Experience	Mean 15.33 (range 4-30, SD 10.873)
Certifications (number of nurses with any certification)	1 (33%)
Highest Level of Education	1 - Master's Degree (33%)

PIVC placement policy and training program developed

Discussion

- Need for more research pertaining to PIVC training programs for home health RNs
- Home health RNs benefited from the PIVC training program which utilized both online video and hands-on training portions
- PIVC insertion competency improved as PIVC insertion knowledge and skills increased
- Unexpected findings: decreased RN knowledge assessment and skills checklist scores

RN Completion of PIVC Insertion Skills Checklist Items

Checklist Item Skill	Number (%) of RNs Who Completed Skill [includes both attempts]
1	3 (100%)
2	3 (100%)
3	3 (100%)
4	3 (100%)
5	3 (100%)
6	3 (100%)
7	3 (100%)
8	3 (100%)
9	2 (67%)
10	3 (100%)
11	3 (100%)
12	3 (100%)
13	2 (67%)
14	3 (100%)
15	3 (100%)
16	3 (100%)
17	3 (100%)
18	3 (100%)
19	3 (100%)
20	3 (100%)
21	3 (100%)
22	3 (100%)
23	3 (100%)
24	3 (100%)
25	3 (100%)
26	3 (100%)
27	3 (100%)
28	2 (67%)

Framework

Stevens Star Model of Knowledge Transformation © 2015 Used with expressed permission

Limitations

- Small home health RN population
- Single site implementation
- Sampling/Membership bias
- COVID-19 risks

Future Implications

- Improve knowledge concerning PIVC training and home health RNs
- PIVC training programs beneficial to home health RNs
- Implementing the study amongst a larger sample size
- Improvements to the training program:
 - Increase hands-on practice time
 - Include information into the training portions that better relate to the PIVC knowledge assessments
- Feasible for a home health company to invest in simulation PIVC supplies and a simulation arm